

AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
E-HELPING HOUSING SOCIETY PROJECT REPORT
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1. TITLE – PROPOSED SYSTEM

The basic concept of this society system, we create global web based application in asp.net with C# language to manage Society with House and Owner of house detail.

We provide platform to register society to our system, and there are many houses according to each society. Each house allocated to owner of house, all the owner are members of our project.

After becoming a member they can login to give his house on rent or sell for all users.

The people can easily find search the rent house or sell house in which society and get contact detail of owner of house by visiting our website.

All members can make online complain related home to society management.

2. Introduction

In this society management system all the society categorize by the number of houses. The people who lives in house they may be a owner of house or tenant of house.

In this era, people are very busy with their routine work, so they do not have time for complain small problem related to houses.

We have developed the system for society member they can make complain form any where any time and we resolve the Complain as soon as possible.

In this system people can easily find address of the house by providing member name.

The Member of our system can give advertise his house for rent and sell easily through our system by login his login detail.

The main purpose of this site is to find out the house for rent and house for buy easily by visiting website.

3. REQUIREMENT SPECIFICATION

SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT

Operating System	Windows 10
Front End	Visual Studio Asp.Net 2010 with C# Language
Back end	SQL SERVER 2008 Database

HARDWARE REQUIREMENT

Processor	Pentium III ,3.45 Dual Core Xeon
RAM	1Gb
Hard Disk	1GB Or More Hard Disk
Accessories	CPU, Keyboard ,Mouse, Printer

4. SYSTEM DESIGN

In this society helping system there are three types of user one is **Admin, Owner of house** or member of website and the third rest of **all other people**.

1. ADMIN

- Admin can manage all the system by login with his username and password.
- Admin can register or add detail of society and create or add detail of number of houses of particular society.
- After crating a house, allocate the house to member and generate username and password for all the member of this system. The member is a owner of house.
- Admin can responsible for solve complain made by any member of the system.
- Admin can manage reports of rent house, sell house and complain.

2. MEMBER or OWNER

- In our society system admin can allocate house to member and member is a owner of house. Member can easily put his house on rent and sell whenever he wants.
- Member can make any complain related to house by login his account and he can change his account detail, contact detail.
- Member can receive message from users regarding to rent or buy his house in his message box

3. USER

- User are the people who just search our website. User can easily find out detail of house or get easily address of the house by providing member name or society name from our search page.
- User can easily know about how many houses are on rent and how many on sell in which society with member detail through our society helping system website.

4.1. DESIGN

Design is the first step in the development phase for any techniques and principles for the purpose of defining a device, a process or system in sufficient detail to permit its physical realization.

Once the software requirements have been analyzed and specified the software design involves three technical activities - design, coding, implementation and testing that are required to build and verify the software.

The design activities are of main importance in this phase, because in this activity, decisions ultimately affecting the success of the software implementation and its ease of maintenance are made. These decisions have the final bearing upon reliability and maintainability of the system. Design is the only way to accurately translate the customer's requirements into finished software or a system.

4.2 USE CASE DIAGRAM

- A **Use Case Diagram** at its simplest is a representation of a user's interaction with the system that shows the relationship between the user and the different use cases in which the user is involved.

4.2.1 ER DIAGRAM

- An **Entity-Relationship** model describes interrelated things of interest in a specific domain of knowledge. A basic ER model is composed of entity types (which classify the things of interest) and specifies relationships that can exist between instances of those entity types.

Entity-Relation Diagram

4.2.2 ACTIVITY DIAGRAM

- **Activity Diagram** is another important diagram in UML to describe the dynamic aspects of the system. Activity Diagram is basically a flowchart to represent the flow from one activity to another activity.

ADMIN - Activity Diagram

MEMBER - Activity Diagram

4.3 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

Data Flow Diagrams show the flow of data from external entities into the system, and from one process to another within the system. There are four symbols for drawing a DFD: Rectangles representing *external entities*, which are sources or destinations of data. Ellipses representing *processes*, which take data as input, validate and process it and output it.

Arrows representing the *data flows*, which can either, be electronic data or physical items.

Open-ended rectangles or a Disk symbol representing *data stores*, including electronic stores such as databases or XML files and physical stores such as filing cabinets or stacks of paper.

Figures are the Data Flow Diagrams for the current system. Each process within the system is first shown as a Context Level DFD and later as a Detailed DFD. The Context Level DFD provides a conceptual view of the process and its surrounding input, output and data stores. The Detailed DFD provides a more detailed and comprehensive view of the interaction among the sub-processes within the system

DFD For Login Of User

5. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

In this section source code of some pages is provided.

Code File: MasterPage.master.cs

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;

public partial class MasterPage : System.Web.UI.MasterPage
{
    DS_SOCIETY.SOCIETY_SELECTDataTable SDT = new
DS_SOCIETY.SOCIETY_SELECTDataTable();
    DS_SOCIETYTableAdapters.SOCIETY_SELECTTableAdapter SAdapter =
new DS_SOCIETYTableAdapters.SOCIETY_SELECTTableAdapter();

    DS_USER.USERMST_SELECTDataTable UDT = new
DS_USER.USERMST_SELECTDataTable();
    DS_USERTableAdapters.USERMST_SELECTTableAdapter UAdapter = new
DS_USERTableAdapters.USERMST_SELECTTableAdapter();

    protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        lbllogin.Text = "";
        if (Page.IsPostBack == false)
        {
            SDT = SAdapter.SelectTOP10();
            GridView1.DataSource = SDT;
            GridView1.DataBind();

        }
    }
    protected void btnlogin_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        UDT = UAdapter.Select_Login(txtuname.Text, txtupass.Text);
    }
}
```

```

if (UDT.Rows.Count > 0)
{
    Session["uid"] = UDT.Rows[0]["UID"].ToString();
    Session["uname"] = txtuname.Text;
    Session["upass"] = txtupass.Text;
    Session["fname"] = UDT.Rows[0]["fname"].ToString();
    Session["email"] = UDT.Rows[0]["email"].ToString();
    Response.Redirect("LHome.aspx");
}
else
{
    lbllogin.Text = "Invalid User !!!";
}
}
protected void GridView1_RowCommand(object sender,
GridViewCommandEventArgs e)
{
    Session["sname"] = e.CommandArgument.ToString();
    Response.Redirect("Societylist.aspx");
}
}

```

Code File: Login.master.cs

```

using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;

public partial class Login : System.Web.UI.MasterPage
{
    DS_SOCIETY.SOCIETY_SELECTDataTable SDT = new
DS_SOCIETY.SOCIETY_SELECTDataTable();
    DS_SOCIETYTableAdapters.SOCIETY_SELECTTableAdapter SAdapter =
new DS_SOCIETYTableAdapters.SOCIETY_SELECTTableAdapter();

```

```
DS_USER.USERMST_SELECTDataTable UDT = new
DS_USER.USERMST_SELECTDataTable();
DS_USERTableAdapters.USERMST_SELECTTableAdapter UAdapter = new
DS_USERTableAdapters.USERMST_SELECTTableAdapter();
```

```
protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    if (Session["uid"] == null)
    {
        Response.Redirect("Default.aspx");
    }
    else
    {
        UDT =
UAdapter.Select_By_UID(Convert.ToInt32(Session["uid"].ToString()));
        Image2.ImageUrl = UDT.Rows[0]["image"].ToString();
        lblname.Text = Session["fname"].ToString();
        if (Page.IsPostBack == false)
        {
            SDT = SAdapter.SelectTOP10();
            GridView1.DataSource = SDT;
            GridView1.DataBind();
        }
    }
}
protected void btnlogin_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
}
protected void Button6_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
}
protected void Button3_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
}
protected void LinkButton1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    Session["uid"] = null;
    Session["img"] = null;
```

```

        Response.Redirect("Default.aspx");
    }
    protected void GridView1_RowCommand(object sender,
GridViewCommandEventArgs e)
    {
        Session["sname"] = e.CommandArgument.ToString();
        Response.Redirect("LSearch.aspx");
    }
}

```

Code File: Home.aspx.cs

```

using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.Linq;
using System.Web;
using System.Web.UI;
using System.Web.UI.WebControls;

public partial class Admin_Home : System.Web.UI.Page
{
    protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        lblmsg.Text = "";
    }
    protected void Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        if (txtuname.Text == "admin" && txtupass.Text == "admin")
        {
            Response.Redirect("AddSociety.aspx");
        }
        else
        {
            lblmsg.Text = "Error !!";
        }
    }
}

```

6. RESULT

6.1 DATABASE TABLES:

UserMst

	Name	Data Type	Allow Nulls
PK	UID	int	<input type="checkbox"/>
	FName	nvarchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	LName	nvarchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Email	nvarchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Mobile	nvarchar(10)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Bdate	datetime	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	HouseID	int	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	SocietyName	nvarchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Member	int	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	UserName	nvarchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Password	nvarchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Image	nvarchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Entrydate	datetime	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

SocietyMst

	Name	Data Type	Allow Nulls	
PK	SID	int	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	SName	nvarchar(500)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Address	nvarchar(500)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	City	nvarchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Pincode	nvarchar(10)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	NoHouse	int	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Image	nvarchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	EntryDate	datetime	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
			<input type="checkbox"/>	

HouseMst

	Name	Data Type	Allow Nulls
PK	HID	int	<input type="checkbox"/>
	BlockNo	int	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Type	nvarchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Detail	nvarchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	SName	nvarchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Image	nvarchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	EntryDate	datetime	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

SellMst

	Name	Data Type	Allow Nulls
PK	SID	int	<input type="checkbox"/>
	HID	int	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	SName	nvarchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	UID	int	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Sell	float	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	EntryDate	datetime	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

RentMst

	Name	Data Type	Allow Nulls
PK	RID	int	<input type="checkbox"/>
	HID	int	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	SName	nvarchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	UID	int	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Rent	float	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	EntryDate	datetime	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

MessageMst

	Name	Data Type	Allow Nulls
PK	MID	int	<input type="checkbox"/>
	FromName	nvarchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	ToName	nvarchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Subject	nvarchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Message	nvarchar(500)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Entrydate	datetime	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

ComplainMst

	Name	Data Type	Allow Nulls
PK	CID	int	<input type="checkbox"/>
	UID	int	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Subject	nvarchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Complain	nvarchar(500)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Reply	nvarchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Status	nvarchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Entrydate	datetime	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
			<input type="checkbox"/>

6.1 Screenshot

HomePage

Admin LoginPage

localhost:63518/Admin/Home.aspx

localhost:63518/Admin/Home.aspx

Apps Gmail YouTube Maps Hospital Managem... Untitled Document...

E-Housing Helping Society

ADMIN LOGIN PANEL

UserName :

Password :

Search the web and Windows

12:00 AM
2/20/2020

Add Society

localhost:63518/Admin/AddSoci... x

localhost:63518/Admin/AddSociety.aspx

Apps Gmail YouTube Maps Hospital Managem... Untitled Document...

E-Housing Helping Society

Welcome

ADD SOCIETY

ADD HOUSE

HOUSE REPORT

ALLOCATE HOUSE

MEMBER REPORT

COMPLAIN

SELL HOUSE REPORT

RENT HOUSE REPORT

LOG OUT

ADD NEW SOCIETY

Society Name :

No of Houses :

Address :

City :

Pincode :

Image : No f...osen

	Image	SocietyName	Address	city	Picode	House
Delete		Akshu	Behind Bus Station	Navi Mumbai	400707	10
Delete		Sarti	Mankhurd	Navi Mumbai	400088	15
Delete		Sarfu	Juinagar	Navi Mumbai	400705	5

Search the web and Windows

12:01 AM
2/20/2020

Add New House To Society

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL localhost:63518/Admin/AddHouse.aspx. The page features a header with the logo for 'E-Housing Helping Society' and a navigation menu on the left with buttons for 'Welcome', 'ADD SOCIETY', 'ADD HOUSE', 'HOUSE REPORT', 'ALLOCATE HOUSE', 'MEMBER REPORT', 'COMPLAIN', 'SELL HOUSE REPORT', 'RENT HOUSE REPORT', and 'LOG OUT'. The main content area is titled 'ADD NEW HOUSE TO SOCIETY' and contains a form with the following fields: 'Society' (a dropdown menu), 'Block No' (a text input), 'House Type' (a dropdown menu), and 'Detail' (a text input). A green 'ADD House' button is positioned below the form. The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the time as 12:04 AM on 2/20/2020.

Allocate House To Member

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL localhost:63518/Admin/AddMember.aspx. The page features the same header and navigation menu as the previous page. The main content area is titled 'ALLOCATE HOUSE TO MEMBER' and contains a form with the following fields: 'First Name' (text input), 'Last Name' (text input), 'Email' (text input), 'Mobile' (text input), 'BirthDate' (a date picker with DD, MM, and YYYY dropdowns), 'Total Member' (text input), 'Society Name' (a dropdown menu), 'House No' (a dropdown menu), 'Photo' (a file upload button labeled 'Choose File' and a 'No f...osen' link), 'UserName' (text input), and 'Password' (text input). A green 'ADD Member' button is positioned below the form. The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the time as 12:05 AM on 2/20/2020.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Conclusion:

The package was designed in such a way that future modifications can be done easily. The following conclusion can be deduced from the development of the project.

- Automation of the entire system improves the efficiency
- It provides a friendly graphical user interface which proves to be better when compared to the existing system.
- It gives appropriate access to the authorized users depending on their permissions.
- It effectively overcomes the delay in communications.
- Updating of information becomes so easier.
- System security, data security and reliability are the striking features.
- The System has adequate scope for modification in future if it is necessary.

Future Scope:

This application avoids the manual work and the problems concern with it. It is an easy way to obtain the information regarding the various travel services that are present in our System.

Well I worked hard in order to present an improved website better than the existing one's regarding the information about the various activities. Still, we found out that the project can be done in a better way.

This project can be enhanced further by Developing a Mobile App. Also we can Develop a Full Fledged accounting module.

The software is flexible enough to be modified and implemented as per future requirements.

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